

Shallow and Uneven Progress towards Global Financial Transparency: Evidence from the Financial Secrecy Index^{*}

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Summary

1. The global financial crisis and leaked documents such as the Panama Papers highlighted the important role of financial secrecy in the global economy. Although international initiatives pressing for more transparency have gained strength, there is little knowledge on how the map of financial secrecy has changed over the past decade and why. To fill in the gap, we use the internationally recognised Financial Secrecy Index and analyse its five editions between 2011 and 2020.
2. We find, first, that financial transparency related to international standards and cooperation improved much more than transparency in the arguably more substantive areas of ownership registration, transparency of legal entities, as well as tax and financial regulation.
3. Second, we document convergence of financial transparency among jurisdictions. While some of the most secretive countries and jurisdictions became more transparent, many with higher transparency in 2011 became relatively more secretive by 2020. This convergence is driven mainly by the most secretive countries and jurisdictions becoming more internationally cooperative.
4. Third, we map the heterogeneity of financial secrecy across the world and classify 71 countries and jurisdictions into five groups, which cut across conventional geographical divisions, highlighting the need to study secrecy in specific contexts. They do, however, show that while OECD countries are relatively more transparent, their former colonies, with continued links with and dependency on former colonial powers, exhibit little improvement.
5. Put together, our findings show that while some progress towards global financial transparency has been achieved, it is shallow and very uneven, with convergence potentially replacing a race-to-the-bottom dynamic.

^{*} This Policy Brief is based on the research paper by Janský, P., Palanský, M., & Wójcik, D. (2023). Shallow and Uneven Progress towards Global Financial Transparency: Evidence from the Financial Secrecy Index. *Geoforum*, 141, 103728. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geoforum.2023.103728>

1. Introduction

Financial secrecy is increasingly recognised as one of the defining features of the global economy, related closely to the issues of corruption, tax evasion and avoidance, as well as lax regulation (Clark et al., 2015). Secrecy helps organised crime and terrorists exploit anonymous shell companies and wealthy individuals hide their assets (Zucman, 2015).

Companies set up **secretive ownership structures** with multiple layers of shell corporations and avoid paying billions of dollars in taxes (Garcia-Bernardo & Janský, 2024; Tørsløv et al., 2023). The global financial crisis and new revelations from leaks of offshore documents such as the recent **Panama, Paradise, and Pandora Papers** have all highlighted the crucial role played by financial secrecy in the globalised world (Janský et al., 2022).

Governments are increasingly responding to excessive financial secrecy with financial transparency policies. Perhaps the most successful of such policies recently is the automatic exchange of information aimed at decreasing tax evasion of individuals. Since 2014 countries that joined the initiative exchange information on each other residents' financial accounts automatically rather than upon request, as was the case earlier (Alstadsæter et al., 2023).

Assessments of both automatic (Hakelberg, 2020) and upon-request information exchanges (Johannessen & Zucman, 2014) exist, but **evidence is scarcer for other important policies** such as registers of beneficial ownership. Meanwhile, other forms of financial secrecy, such as those involving trusts and private foundations, are further away from the policy spotlight.

In this study, we investigate **how the global map of financial secrecy changed** during the 2010s by focusing on two questions. What is the degree of change in financial secrecy over that decade, and how does it compare across different jurisdictions and dimensions of transparency? What factors may explain this change?

While answering the former question involves descriptive exploratory analysis, it is crucial, since to the best of our knowledge no research has examined how the overall landscape of financial secrecy has changed since the global financial crisis, and as explained in the following section, opinions and partial evidence on the matter are divided. It is also a pre-requisite for tackling the latter question concerning the causal mechanisms. Answering these questions has major **implications for understanding global finance and for economic policy**, and hence is most pertinent to financial, economic, and political geography.

2. Methods

In our analysis, we use the best available cross-country information source on financial transparency: the **Financial Secrecy Index**. Until the publication of its first edition by Tax Justice Network in 2009, no comprehensive, cross-country indicators of financial secrecy existed (Cobham et al., 2015).

In this study, we use five editions of the index published between 2011 and 2020. To accommodate methodological developments behind the index, we use the harmonised relative secrecy scores, which are calculated as the ratios of the Financial Secrecy Index secrecy scores to the sample mean in individual years. The relative secrecy scores are suitable for **tracking the extent of financial secrecy over time for 71 countries**

and jurisdictions for which data for the whole period are available, and for various dimensions of financial secrecy.

3. Results

Our analysis reveals three groups of findings. First, financial transparency related to **international standards and cooperation improved much more** than in what could be considered more substantive categories of transparency such as ownership registration, as well as legal, tax and financial regulation.

Second, jurisdictions have become more similar in terms of financial secrecy, with many of the most secretive jurisdictions becoming more transparent, while many less secretive jurisdictions at the start of the 2010s became relatively more secretive over time. This **convergence is driven mainly by the most secretive jurisdictions becoming more internationally cooperative**.

Third, **change in financial transparency has been heterogenous across jurisdictions and not tied to conventional geographical regions**, highlighting the need to study such changes at the individual level of countries and jurisdictions. We offer a typology of change in financial secrecy and divide countries and jurisdictions into five groups: relative transparency, cooperation and domestic improvement, domestic improvement with little cooperation, cooperation with little domestic improvement, and little cooperation with little domestic improvement (Table 1, Figure 1).

Reflecting our findings on convergence and shallow improvement, nearly half of the countries and jurisdictions in our sample, 29 out of 71, exhibit cooperation with little domestic improvement. In contrast, only 13 countries and jurisdictions demonstrate

domestic improvement, including four that improved on the domestic front despite little progress in international collaboration and standards.

4. Conclusions

Our findings document **significant progress towards financial transparency in terms of international standards and cooperation**. Between 2011 and 2020, dozens of countries and jurisdictions have started cooperating much more intensively with others on policies such as automatic exchange of information. At the same time, however, we show that change in other areas of secrecy, such as transparency of ownership, legal entities, and the integrity of tax and financial regulations, international progress has been much more limited, sometimes non-existent. This in turn questions the very benefits of international cooperation and standards. For example, a country or jurisdiction might commit to exchange information automatically, but that can be **toothless if they do not enforce the registration of beneficial owners of its companies**.

Commitments to transparency made through participation in international initiatives do not necessarily produce genuine change. Put bluntly, **jurisdictions may commit to sharing information internationally, but then neglect the collection of information that could and should be shared**. All these observations lead to the conclusion that improvement in financial transparency has been shallow. Overall, we demonstrate that **progress towards global financial transparency during the 2010s has been shallow and uneven**.

What is DemoTrans ?

DemoTrans is an impact-driven research project that will provide theoretically and empirically robust recommendations on how to reinvigorate democratic governance by improving the accountability, transparency, effectiveness and trustworthiness of rule-of-law based institutions and policies.

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Figures

Group	Highly secretive in either 2020 or 2011	Change in secrecy, cat. 1-3 (Ownership registration, Legal entity transparency, Integrity of tax and financial regulation)	Change in secrecy, cat. 4 (International standards and cooperation)	List of jurisdictions
Relative transparency	No	Any	Any	Austria, Belgium, Canada, Cyprus, Denmark, France, Germany, Hungary, India, Ireland, Israel, Italy, Japan, Latvia, Luxembourg, Malta, Portugal, South Korea, Spain, United Kingdom, United States
Cooperation and domestic improvement	Yes	-	-	Bahrain, Ghana, Lebanon, Macao, San Marino, Seychelles, St. Lucia, St. Vincent and the Grenadines, Uruguay
Domestic improvement with little cooperation	Yes	-	+	Botswana, Dominica, Liberia, Philippines
Cooperation with little domestic improvement	Yes	+	-	Andorra, Anguilla, Antigua and Barbuda, Bahamas, Barbados, Bermuda, British Virgin Islands, Cook Islands, Costa Rica, Curacao, Gibraltar, Grenada, Guernsey, Hong Kong, Isle of Man, Jersey, Liechtenstein, Malaysia, Marshall Islands, Mauritius, Monaco, Panama, Samoa, Singapore, St. Kitts and Nevis, Switzerland, Turks and Caicos Islands, United Arab Emirates, Vanuatu
Little cooperation with little domestic improvement	Yes	+	+	Aruba, Belize, Brunei, Cayman Islands, Guatemala, Montserrat, Netherlands, US Virgin Islands

Table 1. Typology of paths in the development of financial secrecy over time. Source: Janský et al. (2023)

Figure 1. Development of financial secrecy categories by geographical groups. Note: The plots show a simple average relative score for all countries and jurisdictions in a given group. Source: Janský et al. (2023)

Further Information:

Janský, P., Palanský, M., & Wójcik, D. (2023). Shallow and Uneven Progress towards Global Financial Transparency: Evidence from the Financial Secrecy Index. *Geoforum*, 141, 103728. <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.geoforum.2023.103728>

DemoTrans is funded by the European Commission in its Horizon Europe framework (grant 101059288). Views and opinions expressed are however those of the author(s) only and do not necessarily reflect those of the European Union or the granting authority. Neither the European Union nor the granting authority can be held responsible for them.

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